

visual observations, are given here.

Soils usually have medium N fertility (0.75% organic C), low to medium available P (20-50 kg/ha), and high available K (350-500 kg/ha). P encourages BGA blooms, but K does not. BGA blooms disappear immediately after K fertilization.

In summer monsoon, river water is the main source of irrigation. It carries heavy silt deposits into rice fields. Water

turbidity reduces incidental radiation and adversely affects photosynthetic algal activity. Moreover, the silt contains 3 to 5 ppm of K oxide, which may act as a mild algicide.

Close, dry season plant spacing results in a closed crop canopy and hinders penetration of solar radiation into the water. Weeds such as *Marsilea quadrifolia* and *M. minuta* may cover the water surface and further decrease

available light.

Several algal grazers are common. Snails are voracious grazers. Snail infestation is largest the first 2 wk after transplanting, which also is the peak period of BGA bloom development. If field water depth increases, snail population increases. Tilapia, grass carp, catla, and rohu fingerlings abound in rice fields and also feed on algae. *S*

Machinery Development and Testing

A wooden frame for transplanting rice

I. M. Bhatti and M. A. Bhutto, Rice Research Institute, Dokri, Sind, Pakistan

Proper plant development occurs only if a crop is well managed from planting to harvest. Management is enhanced with straight rows and evenly spaced hills. We developed an easy-to-handle wooden frame (see figure) to use for line or random transplanting for optimum plant population.

The frame consists of 4, 1-m-long wood strips, 2.5 cm wide and 1 cm thick. All sides have cut markings every 20 cm for 20- × 20 cm spacing. Farmers who

Wooden frame for transplanting rice, Sind, Pakistan.

prefer random planting can transplant 25 plants/ hills. To further facilitate planting, an angle-iron partition in the center can be used to plant 12 hills in one

portion and 13 in another to make 25 hills/m².

The frame has been introduced in farmers' fields. *S*

Announcements

De Datta honored

S. K. De Datta, head of the IRRI Agronomy Department, has received the following awards from the Weed Science Society of the Philippines (WSSP), the Philippine Council for Agriculture Resources Research and Development (PCARRD), the Soil Science Society of America (SSSA), and the American Society of Agronomy (ASA):

- Best Paper Award for a paper titled *Reducing the application volume of 2, 4-D with controlled drop*

applicators in rainfed rice (WSSP),

- Most Outstanding Research and Development Award for the Los Baños Community for a paper titled *Fertilizer application and weed control technology for rice in a resource-scarce Philippine farmers situation* (PCARRD),
- American Fellow Award (SSSA), and
- International Service in Agronomy Award for 1985 (ASA).

De Datta earned his BS degree from Banaras Hindu University and the MS equivalent at the Indian Agricultural Research Institute, both in India, and the PhD at the University of Hawaii, USA. He has been head of the IRRI Agronomy Department since 1967, and

has authored or coauthored more than 200 research and technical papers and three book chapters, and wrote *Principles and practices of rice production*. *S*

Chang lectures published

Six special lectures given by T. T. Chang, head of the IRRI International Rice Germplasm Center, as part of the 1984 Iowa State University Plant Science Lecture Series, Plant Genetic Resources — Key to Future Plant Production, have been published in the Iowa State Journal of Research, Vol. 59, No. 4.

The lectures include Principles of genetic conservation, Collection of crop